

Actual vs Predicted (MinTemp)

Standardized Residuals (MinTemp)

Partial Regression Plot (MinTemp)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.6815$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 0.4061

p-value: 0.5239

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 4.8950

df: 2

p-value: 0.0865

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (MinTemp)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – MinTemp

